

Enhancement in the Fluorescence Intensity of Rhodamine-B by Some Surfactants

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The effect of some nonionic, cationic and anionic surfactants on the fluorescence and absorption studies of Rhodamine-B is presented. Enhancement in the fluorescence intensity of Rhodamine-B takes place by the addition of all the surfactants. The enhancement in fluorescence intensity appears to be due to the disaggregation of the dye molecules by interaction with surfactant micelles with no basic change in the structure of the dye.

THE spectral colour changes observed during the interaction of ionic dyes with ionic detergents in solution have attracted the attention of many workers¹⁻⁷. Harkins² and Co-workers after studying various systems proposed dimer and multimer formation of dye molecules in the detergent micelle. The influence of surfactants on the fluorescence intensity of dyes has been studied by Harada and Toya⁸ and Ghosh⁹. Ghosh has reported that the fluorescence intensity of methylene blue initially decreases and subsequently increases on addition of sodium lauryl sulphate. Harada and co-workers have shown that the fluorescence intensity of certain dyes can be influenced by addition of some esters and long-chain fatty acids, amongst which polyethylene monoleate and poly(oxyethylene) sorbitain monoleate were the most effective.

Enhancement in the intensity of some fluorescent brightening agents used on fiber has been reported by Padhye¹⁰ and coworkers. Hsin-Chouchiang and Aaron Lukton¹¹ have reported that enhancement in the fluorescence intensity of 2-p-Toluidinylnaphthalene-6-sulphonate (TNS) by the addition of sodium lauryl sulphate is due to the interaction between the micelles of the sodium lauryl sulphate and TNS.

These investigations present the influence on the fluorescence intensity and absorbance of Rhodamine-B by the addition of anionic, cationic and nonionic surfactants. All the surfactants have been found to cause enhancement in fluorescence intensity of Rhodamine-B although there is no marked change in its absorption spectra in the presence of surfactants. The enhancement in the fluorescence intensity appears to be due to the interaction between the surfactant and the dye molecules.

Experimental

The fluorescence studies were made with Aminco-Bowman Spectrofluorophotometer with a cell of 1 cm path length. The absorption studies were made on 'Carl Zeiss' Spectrophotometer 'SPBKO'. All the reagents were of reagent grade.

The following surfactants were used :—

- Cationic : i) Dodcyl benzene sodium sulphonate (DBSS).
- ii) Dioctyl sodium sulphasuccinate (DSSS).
- Cationic : i) Cetyl trimethyl ammoniumbromide (CTAB).
- ii) Cetyl pyridinium bromide (CPB).
- Nonionic : i) Polyoxyethylene sorbitain monoleate (Tween-80).
- ii) Triton X-100 (Tx-100).

Results

Cationic surfactants : The wave length chosen for excitation of Rhodamine-B was 545 nm and the fluorescence measurements were made at 578 nm. Enhancement in fluorescence intensity of Rhodamine-B upto 50% of its original value occurred by the addition of CTAB. In case of CPB the enhancement was found to be less. No change in the fluorescence peak wavelength was observed on addition of the surfactants. It was also observed that the fluorescence intensity reached a limiting value at a particular concentration of surfactant. No marked change in the wave length of absorption peaks was found to occur on addition of the surfactants.

Anionic surfactants : Marked enhancement in the fluorescence intensity was observed on the addition of DBSS and DSSS. It was further seen that an initial decrease in the fluorescence intensity took place at lower concentration of surfactants and subsequently increase in intensity occurred on further addition of the surfactant. The observations are shown in Fig. 1. The shape and λ_{max} of the curve remained the same throughout the change in the intensity. There however appeared a small shift of 2-4 nm in the λ_{max} of the absorption spectra towards longer wave lengths by the addition of surfactants. The influence on the fluorescence intensity by changing the concentration of surfactants is given in

TABLE 1—VARIATION OF FLUORESCENCE INTENSITY OF RHODAMINE-B WITH VARYING CONCENTRATION OF SURFACTANTS

Conc. of Rhodamine-B = $10^{-5}M$						$\lambda_{ex} = 545 \text{ nm}$		$\lambda_{em} = 578 \text{ nm}$				
F. I. = Fluorescence Intensity												
S. No.	Conc. of DBSS in/%	F. I.*	Conc. of DSSS in/%	F. I.	Conc. of Tx-100 in/%	F. I.	Conc. of Tween-80 in/%	F. I.	Conc. of CTAB in/%	F. I.	Conc. of CPB in/%	F. I.
1.	0.000	80	0.00	80	0.000	80	0.000	80	0.000	80	0.000	80
2.	0.01	53	0.01	82	0.004	78	0.005	83	0.005	83	0.005	84
3.	0.02	36	0.05	78	0.008	82	0.010	83	0.010	87	0.010	88
4.	0.05	66	0.10	76	0.020	84	0.025	84	0.030	91	0.030	90
5.	0.07	144	0.15	80	0.040	87	0.040	84	0.050	97	0.050	92
6.	0.10	159	0.20	88	0.048	90	0.050	86	0.070	103	0.070	92
7.	0.20	165	0.25	95	0.060	94	0.100	91	0.080	111	0.080	92
8.	0.50	165	0.30	103	0.080	95	0.200	97	0.090	117	0.100	92
9.	0.60	165	0.50	107	0.160	95	0.300	106	0.100	120	—	—
10.	0.80	165	0.60	107	0.240	95	0.450	117	—	—	—	—
11.	0.9	165	0.80	107	0.320	95	0.800	120	—	—	—	—

Fig. 1—Variation of fluorescence intensity of Rhodamine-B on varying the concentration of DBSS.

Fig. 3—Absorption spectra of Rhodamine-B $10^{-5}M$

- (i) ○—○—○ pure Rhodamine-B.
- (ii) ●—●—● with .02% DBSS.
- (iii) X—X—X with .05% DBSS.
- (iv) △—△—△ with .50% DBSS.

Fig. 2—Fluorescence spectra of Rhodamine-B with DBSS

- (i) ○—○—○ Pure Rhodamine-B $10^{-5}M$.
- (ii) ●—●—● with .02% of DBSS.
- (iii) X—X—X with .90% of DBSS.

Table 1. The fluorescence and absorption spectra are given in Fig. 2 and 3 respectively, in presence of DBSS. Limiting values of fluorescence intensity occurred in the following order

$$DBSS > DSSS$$

Nonionic surfactants: Enhancement in the intensity of fluorescence occurred on addition of nonionic surfactants. Initially the increase in the fluorescence intensity was small but was followed by a large enhancement on addition of excess of nonionic surfactants. The shape of fluorescence spectra however remained unaltered. The observations are given in Table 1.

The absorption spectral studies show that although the λ_{max} remained the same, there occurred a small decrease in the absorbance on adding Tx-100. In

case of Tween-80 the peak height first decreased and later increased. while a shift of 2-4 nm occurred towards longer wave lengths.

Discussion :

The enhancement in the fluorescence intensity on the addition of cationic and nonionic surfactants appears to be due to the disaggregation of dye molecules. The fluorescence is mainly due to the monomeric form and its surfactant complex⁴. In aqueous solutions the reduced fluorescence of the dye is due to its aggregated form. On addition of surfactants to the dye solution interaction between dye and surfactant micelles result in the formation of dye-surfactant complex. This process would lead to disaggregation of aggregated dye molecules resulting in the enhancement in fluorescence intensity.

Absorption studies in all the cases show no change in shape of the spectra. The absorption peak remain nearly unaltered on the addition of the surfactants, but in some cases a small perceptible shift occurs toward longer wave lengths. This confirms that no structural change occurs on addition of surfactant which is expected in a simple disaggregation process. However shift in the peak wave length on the addition of surfactants indicates the presence of bonding between dye-surfactant molecules. Although sharp increase in the peak height occurs in the fluorescence spectra on the addition of surfactants, its shape remains practically unaltered excepting for a small shift in peak which occurs towards longer wave lengths.

With anionic surfactants the fluorescence intensity decreases at lower concentration of surfactants but later increases at higher concentration. Due to the cationic nature of the dye an electrostatic attraction

between dye and surfactant would occur. Thus there would be an additional electrostatic attraction which would result in further aggregation of dye molecules at lower concentration of surfactant. Subsequently at higher surfactant concentration the forces of disaggregation would predominate due to dye-surfactant micelles interaction which would result in enhancement in fluorescence intensity. The absorption and fluorescence spectral studies confirm this view.

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